

DESCRIPTORS FOR A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON SOCIAL SCIENCES (DESLOCIS)

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Getrudix, Manuel¹; Romero-Luis, Juan²; Carbonell-Alcocer, Alejandro³

¹ [ORCID](#) Associate Professor at Universidad Rey Juan Carlos,

² [ORCID](#) Pre-doctoral researcher hired by the Spanish National University Teacher Training Programme (FPU) at Universidad Rey Juan Carlos

³ [ORCID](#) Pre-doctoral researcher hired 2020 Call for Personnel in Training at the Universidad Rey Juan Carlos (own Research Plan)

DESCRIPTION

The analysis model for a Systematic Literature Review on Social Sciences (DESLOCIS) is a framework for the evaluation of scientific literature related to the specific characteristics of publications in the social sciences.

The aim of the model is to identify the design, data collection and analysis of scientific publications so that it distinguishes approaches and theories in existing and emerging research areas.

The model has been developed within the framework of Comciencia Project: Effective, Efficient and Responsible Communication for Competitive Research Projects CSO2017-82875-C2-1-R funded by the Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness (MINECO), the State Research Agency (AEI) and the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF).

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ANALYSIS VARIABLES

[1] Qualitative o Quantitative; [2] Nominal (QL), Ordinal (OL), Interval (QT), Discrete o Continuous (CT)

Variable	QL/QT [1]	N/O/I/C [2]	Value	Definition
Type of perspective	QL	N	Research Educative/Teaching innovation	<p>Perspective from which the study is approached.</p> <p>Research: research papers for use, which have a common structure of a research article and the objective of which is to present the research results.</p> <p>Educative/Teaching innovation: publications which describe interventions or propose models for teaching innovation.</p>
Scope of the object of study	QL	N	Communication/Actions Communication/Communication Agents Communication/Audiences Communication/Communication channels Communication/Communication in the Digital Context Communication/Impact Communication/Communication Models Communication/Institutional Communication Communication/Communication Processes Communication/Communication formats Communication/Communication Techniques Communication/Communication Theories Communication/Other: Social Networks Discourse Education/Digital Literacy Education/Learning Context Education/Scientific method Education/Active Methods Education/School organisation Education/Critical and responsible thinking Education/Educational resources for learning Education/Learning outcomes Education/Other: Ecological Literacy Education/Other: Entrepreneurship Education Policies/Public Engagement Policies/RRI Policies/Programmes, plans and policies Policies/Competitive public calls	<p>Scope in which the object of study of the research article is classified.</p>
Field of knowledge approach/Research Discipline	QL	N	Arts and Humanities Science Health Sciences	<p>Field of knowledge from which the study is approached.</p>

Variable	QL/QT [1]	N/O/I/C [2]	Value	Definition
			Social and Legal Sciences Engineering and Architecture	
Type of research	QL	N	Descriptive Comparative Analytical Explanatory Participative	Type of research of the study.
Classification of objectives [M1, M2 y M3]	QL	N	Act Analyse Resemble Associate Characterise Categorise Classify Codify Compare Contrast Criticise Define Deconstruct Describe Discover Detect Detail Determine Diagnose Differentiate List Specify Establish Estimate Study Evaluate Identify Intervene Modify Present Observe Participate Introduce Propose Reveal No value	Study objectives that are not explicitly stated.
Declaration of objectives	QL	N	Objectives are declared; Objectives are not declared;	It determines whether the objectives are stated in the article or not.

Variable	QL/QT [1]	N/O/I/C [2]	Value	Definition
Declaration of hypothesis	QL	N	Hypothesis are declared; Hypothesis are not declared;	It determines whether the hypothesis are stated in the article or not.
Declaration of study universe	QL	N	Study universe is declared; Study universe is not declared;	It determines whether the study universe is declared or not
Sampling techniques	QL	N	Structural sampling ; Intentional sampling; Probabilistic sampling ; Significant population sampling ; Sample not indicated; Not applicable;	Saming techniques used in the study
Sample size	QL	O	1 to 50; 51 to 100; 101 to 200; 201 to 500; 501 to 1000; 1001 to 2000; Over 2000;	It determines the simple size
Information collection technique	QL	O	1; Over 2;	How many techniques are used in the study
Dominant information collection technique and Secondary information collection technique	QL	N	Conversational techniques/Delphi; Conversational techniques/Groups discussions; Conversational techniques/Personal Interviews/Open interviews; Conversational techniques/Personal Interviews/Semi-structured interviews; Conversational techniques/Personal Interviews/Closed interviews; Conversational techniques/Personal Interviews /Mixed interviews; Conversational techniques/Focus group; Conversational techniques/Social Networks; Conversational techniques/ Other: Social Networks Discourse; Documentary techniques/Content analysis; Documentary techniques/Discourse analysis; Documentary techniques/Documentary analysis; Documentary techniques/Variou; Documentary techniques/Not Stated; Surveys/Attitude survey; Surveys /Opinion survey; Surveys /Variou; Surveys/Not stated; Experimental techniques/Field experiments; Experimental techniques/Group experiments; Experimental techniques/Subject experiments; Observational techniques/Self-observation; Observational techniques/Systematic; Observational techniques/Participatory observation; N/A;	The dominant data collection technique used in the study. If only one: the data collection technique.

Variable	QL/QT [1]	N/O/I/C [2]	Value	Definition
Source of data obtained [Multi-instance 1] [Multi-instance 2]	QL	N	NC/NP; Numerical primary data; Non-numerical primary data; Numerical secondary data; Non-numerical secondary data; No value;	The type of data source, and its numerical or non-numerical nature, used in the study.
Nature of data [Multi-instance 1] [Multi-instance 2]	QL	N	Continuous quantitative data; Discrete quantitative data; Binary qualitative data; Categorical qualitative data; No value;	The nature of the data obtained and used in the study.
Data collection It is not a multi-instance variable because it coincides that there is none with two values. But it could be multistantiated since it can have more than two values.	QL	N	Declarations; Observation; Experiments; Models or simulations; No value;	Typology of the data used in the study according to the way in which they were obtained.
Level of formalisation at a theoretical level	QL	O	Theory; Principle; Models; No value;	Level of formalization at the theoretical level between: theory (more formal), principle and model (less formal), according to the theories, principles or models explicitly mentioned in the article. The most formal always prevails in case several are found.
Branch of knowledge theoretical framing			Art and humanities Sciences Health sciences Social and legal sciences Engineering and architecture	The dominant branch of knowledge in which the theories, models and principles explicitly mentioned in the article are framed.
Number of Analysis techniques	QL	O	1; Over;	How many analysis techniques have been used for the study.
Predominant analysis technique	QL	N	Qualitative analysis/Analytical induction Qualitative analysis/Grounded Theory Qualitative analysis/Semiotic-structural Qualitative analysis/Document Study Quantitative techniques/Univariable Quantitative techniques/Multivariable/Descriptive statistics Quantitative techniques/Multivariable/Non-parametric statistics (Mann Whitney) Quantitative techniques/Multivariable/Analysis of variance (ANOVA) Quantitative techniques/Bivariable/Descriptive statistics Quantitative techniques/Multivariable/ Factorial analysis (CFA Confirmatory factor analysis) Quantitative techniques/Multivariable/Chi square (Pearson) Quantitative techniques/Multivariable/Rough Set Analysis (RSA) Quantitative techniques/Multivariable	The dominant analysis technique used in the study. If only one: the data collection technique.

Variable	QL/QT [1]	N/O/I/C [2]	Value	Definition
			Quantitative techniques /Exploratory Multivariable Social Network Analysis Techniques/Text Mining Social Network Analysis Techniques/Reality Mining Social Network Analysis Techniques/Sentiment Analysis Social Network Analysis Techniques/Community detection Social Network Analysis Techniques/Dynamic network analysis Social Network Analysis Techniques/Dissemination of information Social Network Analysis Techniques/Urban Network Analysis Social Network Analysis Techniques/Reality Mining NC/NP	
Secondary analysis technique	QL	N	Qualitative analysis/Analytical induction Qualitative analysis/Grounded Theory Qualitative analysis/Semiotic-structural Qualitative analysis/Document Study Quantitative techniques/Multivariable/Descriptive statistics Quantitative techniques/Multivariable/Non-parametric statistics (Mann Whitney) Quantitative techniques/Bivariable/Descriptive statistics Quantitative techniques/Multivariable/ Factorial analysis (CFA Confirmatory factor analysis) Quantitative techniques/Multivariable/Chi square (Pearson) Quantitative techniques/Multivariable/Rough Set Analysis (RSA) Quantitative techniques/Multivariable Quantitative techniques /Exploratory Multivariable Social Network Analysis Techniques/Text Mining Social Network Analysis Techniques/Sentiment Analysis Social Network Analysis Techniques/Community detection Social Network Analysis Techniques/Dynamic network analysis Social Network Analysis Techniques/Dissemination of information Social Network Analysis Techniques/Urban Network Analysis Social Network Analysis Techniques/Reality Mining Not applicable	The secondary analysis technique used in the study.

BIBLIOMETRIC DATA

Source: <https://harzing.com/resources/publish-or-perish/manual/using/query-results/metrics>

Temática	Vairable	QL/QT [1]	N/O/ I/C [2]	Valores	Definition
	Year	QT		From 2009 to 2019	Year of publication.
	Source	QT	N		Journal or Conferences where the article has been published.
	Publisher	QT	N		Publisher.
	Type	QL	N	Article Procedeen paper	Publication type.
Data Metrics	Cites [S,GS,W]	QT	C	Ordinal numbers, no decimals.	The sum of the citation counts across all currently selected results.
	CitesPerYear [S,GS,W]	QT	C	Ordinal numbers, 2 decimals.	Citations/year. Set to citation count divided by the age of the article; result is rounded to 2 decimal digits
	CitesPerAuthor [S,GS,W]	QT	C	Ordinal numbers, no decimals.	Set to citation count divided by the number of the authors, rounded to the nearest whole number.
	Author Count	QT	C	Ordinal numbers, no decimals.	Number of authors.
	Age	QT	C	From 0 to 10.	Age of the paper. Calculated as year of reference date - year of publication

FUNDING

This model has been developed within the framework of Comciencia Project: Effective, Efficient and Responsible Communication for Competitive Research Projects CSO2017-82875-C2-1-R funded by the Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness (MINECO), the State Research Agency (AEI) and the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF); and has received funds from: BIOTRES-CM project (S2018/EMT-4344), funded by the Community of Madrid and the European Regional Development Fund; 2020 Call for Personnel in Training at the Rey Juan Carlos University (own Research Plan; award number: PREDOC 20-008); and the Spanish Ministry of Education University Teacher Training Programme (FPU, award number: FPU18/02161).